

Synthesis and antibacterial properties of some *N*-1,2,4-triazolyquinazolinones[†]

B. Shivarama Holla*, P. M. Akberali[#] and M. K. Shivananda

Department of Chemistry, Mangalore University, Mangalagangothri-574 199, India

Manuscript received 9 July 1998, revised 17 May 1999, accepted 22 June 1999

A series of 1,2,4-triazolyquinazolinones have been prepared and characterized on the basis of analytical and spectral data. The compounds have been screened for their antibacterial properties.

In view of the varied biological properties of quinazolinones¹ and *s*-triazoles² and in continuation of our work on quinazolinone derivatives³, we have synthesized some 2-substituted-3-[5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl]quinazolin-4-ones and screened for their antibacterial properties.

Results and Discussion

The required triazolyquinazolinones were prepared via condensation of 4-amino-5-mercaptotriazoles with benzoxazinones. The 3-alkyl substituted-4-amino-5-mercapto-*s*-triazoles⁴ and 3-aryl-4-amino-5-mercapto-*s*-triazoles⁵ were prepared according to the reported procedures. On the other hand, acetic anhydride treatment of anthranilic acid yielded 2-methyl-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one (1, R¹ = CH₃) in good yield. 2-(2-Chlorophenyl)-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one (1, R¹ = C₆H₅Cl) was similarly prepared by treating *o*-chlorobenzoyl chloride with anthranilic acid in presence of dry pyridine. 3-Substituted-4-amino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles (2) were then condensed with 2-substituted-3,1-benzoxazin-4-one (1) in presence of phosphorus oxychloride to afford the hitherto unknown 2-substituted-3-(5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazol-4-yl)-quinazolin-4-ones (3) (Scheme 1).

The physical and spectral data of compounds 3a-q are given in Experimental section. The mass spectrum of 3a was found to be consistent with its structure (Scheme 2).

Antibacterial activity: *N*-Triazolyquinazolinones 3e, 3g and 3i were screened for their *in vitro* antibacterial activity against *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, *B. subtilis* and *S. aureus* by disc-diffusion method⁶ using nitrofurazone as the standard drug. Among the compounds tested, only 3g showed good antibacterial activity against *B. subtilis* (zone of inhibition, 10.25 mm) as compared to that of the standard (10.0 mm).

Experimental

M.ps. were determined by capillary method and are un-

	R ¹	R		R ¹	R
3a	CH ₃	CH ₃	3i	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₂
b	CH ₃	C ₂ H ₅	j	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	CH ₃
c	CH ₃	C ₃ H ₇	k	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	C ₂ H ₅
d	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	l	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	C ₃ H ₇
e	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	m	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	C ₆ H ₅
f	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ OCH ₂	n	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄
g	CH ₃	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ OCH ₂	o	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ OCH ₂
h	CH ₃	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₂	p	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ OCH ₂
			q	<i>o</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₂

Scheme 1

corrected. Electronic spectra (DMF) were recorded on a Beckman 24 spectrophotometer, ir spectra (nujol) on a Perkin-Elmer 529 spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) or Bruker WH-200 (270 MHz) spectrometer using tetramethylsilane as internal standard, and mass spectra on a Jeol JMS-D 300 spectrometer (70 eV).

2-Methyl-3-[3-(*p*-chlorophenyl)-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl]quinazolin-4-one (3e): 5-(*p*-Chlorophenyl)-3-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (2; 10 mmol) and 2-methyl-3,1-

[†]Presented at the 83rd Session of the Indian Science Congress held at Patiala, 1996.

[#]Present address: Plasma Laboratories Ltd., 120 A/B, Industrial Area, Baikampady, New Mangalore-575 011, India.

Scheme 2. Mass spectral fragmentation pattern of triazolopyquinazolinone (3a).

benzoxazin-4-one (1; 10 mmol) were suspended in dry toluene (50 ml) and phosphorus oxychloride (11 mmol) was added with stirring. The solution was refluxed for 3 h, then cooled, excess of toluene removed and the residue digested with water (100 ml) and concentrated HCl (10 ml) on a water-bath. The solution was then cooled to room temperature, neutralized with aqueous sodium bicarbonate and the resultant solid was crystallized from ethanol, (88%), m.p. 273°; λ_{\max} 270 ($\epsilon = 1685$), 320 nm ($\epsilon = 1072$); λ_{\max} 2926 (SH and NH taut.), 1716 (C=O), 1614 (C=N), 1467 and 1362 cm^{-1} (CH def.); δ (270 MHz, DMSO- d_6), 2.5 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.7–8.1 (8H, m), 14.8 (1H, bs, SH); m/z , 369 (M⁺), 354 (M-CH₃), 336 (M-SH), 308 (336-CO), 295 (M⁺-SH-CH₃CN), 219 (295-benzyne).

Similarly other compounds were prepared (yields 84–91%): **3a**, m.p. 230°, m/z 273 (M⁺), 240 (M-SH), 156 (M-CH₃CN-benzyne); **b**, 218°, λ_{\max} 270 ($\epsilon = 1435$), 320 nm ($\epsilon = 445$), δ 1.1–1.4 (3H, t, CH₃), 2.2–2.5 (2H, q, CH₂),

2.4 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.3–8.2 (4H, m, ArH), 13.7 (1H, bs, SH); **c**, 248°; **d**, 310°, ν_{\max} 1719 (C=O), 2926 (NH/SO), 1467 and 1368 cm^{-1} (CH def); **f**, 201°; **g**, 283°, δ 2.5 (3H, s, CH₃), 5.1 (1H, d, J 13.4 Hz, CH₂, aryloxymethyl), 5.3 (1H, d, J 13.4, CH₂, aryloxymethyl), 14.2 (1H, bs, SH); **h**, 251°, δ 2.0 (3H, s, *o*-tolyl), 2.3 (3H, s, CH₃, quinazolinone), 4.9 (1H, d, J 13.4 Hz, CH₂, aryloxymethyl), 5.1 (1H, d, J 13.4 Hz, CH₂, aryloxymethyl), 6.7–8.1 (8H, m, ArH), 14.1 (1H, bs, SH), m/z 279 (M⁺), 305 (M-SH-CH₃CN), 229 (305-benzyne), 262, 247, 155, 141, 108 (%), 84; **i**, 215°; **j**, 190°, m/z 269 (M⁺), 334 (M-Cl), 306 (334-CO); **k**, 155°, δ 1.2 (3H, t, CH₃), 2.4 (2H, q, CH₂), 5.1 (1H, d, J 13.3 Hz, CH₂, aryloxymethyl), 5.3 (1H, d, J 13.3 Hz, CH₂, aryloxymethyl), 6.8–8.1 (8H, m, ArH and quinazolinone), 11.4 (1H, bs, exchangeable with D₂O); **l**, 175°; **m**, 170°; **n**, 179°; **o**, 165°; **p**, 215°, ν_{\max} 2900 (NH/SO), 1720 (C=O), 1600 cm^{-1} (C=N), m/z 495 (M⁺), 460 (M⁺-Cl).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Head, R.S.I.C., C.D.R.I., Lucknow, and S.I.F., Bangalore, for providing microanalysis and spectral data. Two of the authors (P.M.A. and M.K.S.) are grateful to U.G.C. and C.S.I.R., New Delhi, respectively, for awards of research fellowships.

References

- V. J. Ram and M. Verma, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1991, **30**, 1119; V. G. Reddy and P. S. N. Reddy, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1992, **31**, 764; B. R. Shah, J. J. Bhatt, H. H. Patel, N. K. Undavia, P. B. Trivedi and N. C. Desai, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1995, **34**, 201; A. A. F. Wasfy, F. A. Yassin and A. M. F. Eissa, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1995, **34**, 537.
- H. L. Yale and J. J. Piala, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1966, **9**, 42.
- B. S. Holla, P. M. Akberali and M. K. Shivananda, *Boll. Chim. Farm.*, 1996, **135**, 351; B. S. Holla, M. T. Padmaja, M. K. Shivananda and P. M. Akberali, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1998, **17**, 715.
- H. Baeyer, C. F. Kroeger and G. Busse, *Ann. Chim.*, 1960, **637**, 135; K. S. Dhaka, J. Mohan, V. K. Chadha and H. K. Pujari, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, **12**, 288.
- J. R. Reid and N. D. Heindel, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1976, **13**, 925.
- R. Cruickshank, J. P. Duguid, B. P. Marmion and R. H. A. Swain, "Medical Microbiology", Churchill Livingstone, New York, 1975, Vol. II.